

Modeling Dipolar Nonprotogenic Solvents with PC-SAFT-Type Equations of State: Pure Substance Properties

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ABSTRACT: Dipolar nonprotogenic solvents (DNSs) are interesting and important substances widely used in various applications, including organic syntheses, sustainable fuels, and organic electronics. They exhibit intriguing molecular and interactional properties, characterized by large dipole moments, strong dipole–dipole interactions, hydrogen bond (HB) acceptor ability, and the formation of dimer complexes. The latter aspect, along with the traditional view of DNSs as having a weak or negligible HB donor ability, has led to debates about the origin (dipolar vs HB) of these complexes. Therefore, modeling and predicting the thermodynamic properties of DNSs is challenging and requires sophisticated approaches. The PC-SAFT-type

equations of state are powerful tools for describing the macroscopic thermodynamic properties of fluid systems, including DNSs. In this work, we explore and compare the performance of various modeling strategies within PC-SAFT for pure DNSs, including nonpolar, explicitly dipolar, and pseudo-associating approaches. These strategies differ in the treatment of the strongly dipolar character of DNSs. The PC-SAFT parameter sets for each DNS and strategy were determined *de novo* by fitting them to reliable reference data on the liquid density and vapor pressure. A comprehensive computational evaluation of the results for the fluid-phase thermodynamic properties of six DNSs in their pure form is provided, and the merits and drawbacks of the considered strategies are discussed. The pure-compound parameter values are also analyzed. The best results are obtained from the pseudo-association strategy, which considers DNSs to be self-associating with both HB acceptor and donor sites, followed by an explicitly dipolar approach with optimized dipole moment values. Surprisingly, a nonpolar strategy without any explicit dipolar treatment provides results comparable to those of the above models. It is also demonstrated that optimized or gas-phase dipole moments of DNSs are significantly better for use within PC-SAFT in the context of pure DNSs than those related to the liquid phase calculated quantum-mechanically using a polarizable continuum model. Possible explanations for these observations are provided.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dipolar nonprotogenic solvents (DNSs, or dipolar aprotic solvents¹), such as acetonitrile, *N,N*-dimethylformamide, γ -valerolactone, or sulfolane, are important class of chemical substances. They possess a strongly dipolar character, characterized by a large permanent dipole moment. For example, acetonitrile and γ -valerolactone exhibit gas-phase dipole moment values of 3.9 and 4.7 D, respectively, which is more than double the dipole moment of water (1.85 D).² However, they are typically considered to lack sufficiently labile (acidic) hydrogen atoms to act as hydrogen bond donors.¹

The pronounced dipolar character of DNSs is anticipated to significantly influence the macroscopic thermodynamic properties of both pure DNSs and their mixtures with other substances.³ DNSs exhibit several intriguing physicochemical properties, including a high relative permittivity, low volatility, high boiling point, and favorable miscibility and solubilization behavior.^{4–7} Specifically, they are typically completely miscible with water, alcohols, and other DNSs, while they show a limited miscibility with, for example, *n*-alkanes.^{8–14}

DNSs are used in a broad spectrum of applications. For example, they include renewable green solvents derived from biomass,^{13,15–17} sustainable energy sources,^{6,10} precursors for other chemicals, reaction media for organic synthesis,^{18,19} or efficient green solvents for the fabrication and processing of organic semiconductors,^{20–24} for example, in the context of organic photovoltaics and thin-film transistors.

For high-throughput screening of solvents for organic molecules or to evaluate whether a DNS is a suitable solvent for a given application, knowledge and description of its thermodynamic behavior are crucial. State-of-the-art predictive thermodynamic models for phase equilibria in mixtures, such as

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modified UNIFAC²⁵ or COSMO-type models,^{26,27} cannot provide a pressure dependence of thermodynamic properties or predict properties of pure substances like the liquid density, vaporization properties, and heat capacity, which are important for a complete picture of the thermodynamic behavior. (However, in the case of COSMO-type models, additional treatments have been proposed to enable the prediction of some of these properties^{28,29}). This highlights the importance of equations of state (EOSs), which provide comprehensive thermodynamic information on both mixtures and pure substances. The statistical associating fluid theory (SAFT) EOSs, including the perturbed-chain SAFT (PC-SAFT)^{30–32} as one of the most successful representatives, are rooted in a solid theory based on statistical thermodynamics.^{33–35} They can explicitly (at least qualitatively) account for various types of interactions, including both dipolar and association interactions that play a crucial role in systems containing DNSs (see the discussion below). The association interactions usually, but not necessarily, refer to hydrogen bonding (HB). Therefore, these advanced EOSs are used to model the thermodynamic properties of a broad spectrum of chemical systems, including complex substances with intricate interactional and structural characteristics, such as pharmaceuticals,^{36,37} ionic liquids,^{38,39} and polymers.^{40,41} While the literature on the application of PC-SAFT to mixtures containing DNSs is vast (e.g., refs 11, 12, and 42–46), specific applications to the properties of pure DNSs are less frequent.^{32,47,48}

To choose an appropriate modeling strategy for DNSs that adequately accounts for their molecular properties and intermolecular interactions, a deeper understanding of these important factors is essential. Figure 1 shows the molecular

Figure 1. Molecular structures and electrostatic potential maps of some exemplary DNSs (calculated quantum-mechanically in Gaussian 16 software⁵² at the MP2/aug-cc-pVTZ level of theory). From left to right: γ -valerolactone, propylene carbonate, and acetonitrile. The red and blue regions represent negative and positive charges, respectively.

structures and electrostatic potential maps of three exemplary DNSs: γ -valerolactone (GVL), propylene carbonate (PC), and acetonitrile (ACN). Molecules of DNSs exhibit a substantial hot spot of increased electron density corresponding to lone electron pairs in electronegative atoms (O, N, or S). Taking GVL as an example, its hot spot is given by the close proximity of carbonyl and alkoxy oxygen atoms, where an increased electron density is concentrated, which also results in its high HB acceptor ability (specifically, the double-bonded carbonyl oxygen is the dominant HB acceptor site^{49–51}). Because DNS molecules typically feature only one such hot spot and the rest of the molecular surface generally exhibits a lower charge density, these permanent asymmetries in their electron distributions are responsible for their large permanent dipole moments.

With regard to pure substances, the large dipole moments entail strong dipole–dipole interactions between DNS mole-

cules, leading to significant molecular ordering in the liquid phase and even the formation of DNS...DNS dimer complexes. This phenomenon has been demonstrated, for example, by Aparicio and Alcalde,⁸ Richardi et al.,⁵³ and Knözinger and Wittenbeck⁵⁴ for GVL, ACN, and acetone, respectively. They also revealed that these dimers preferentially have an out-of-plane arrangement with an antiparallel (head-to-tail) orientation of the molecular dipoles. However, Świergiel et al.⁵⁵ later found the parallel in-plane arrangement to be the most favorable mutual configuration of GVL and PC molecules in their liquid-phase complexes, on the basis of static permittivity measurements. Nevertheless, these and other^{51,56–58} studies clearly indicate the existence of strong dipolar interactions between DNS molecules and their tendency to aggregate in the liquid phase, which influences the macroscopic thermodynamic behavior of pure DNSs. The important long-range dipole–dipole interactions can explicitly be taken into account in PC-SAFT through a dipolar contribution^{3,32,59–61} (see Section 2.1).

The tendency of DNS molecules to form aggregates raises questions about the presence of specific short-range HB interactions in their pure form, in addition to dipole–dipole interactions, despite not apparently having HB donor ability.⁶² (Such HB interactions could be described by the association contribution of PC-SAFT.) Interestingly, the results of respective studies in the literature can be both in favor and against the existence of HB between DNS molecules, depending on individual DNSs, conditions, and research means (experimental or computational). For example, Aparicio and Alcalde,⁸ using both experimental and computational techniques, have dismissed the existence of HB interactions between molecules of GVL both in out-of-plane and in-plane dimer arrangements. They found that the GVL dimer complexes and their properties (e.g., interaction energy and bond distance) did not meet the criteria for being considered to originate from HB interactions. As a result, the complexes are assumed to have a dipolar nature.^{8,55} This would suggest that DNS molecules are not self-associative in the traditional sense of HB, mainly because they lack HB donor sites in form of a protic hydrogen atom, which is also supported by their Kamlet–Taft solvatochromic parameters.⁶² However, for the GVL–ethanol system, Mbaiwa and Nyepetsi⁵¹ recently showed through computational means [classical molecular dynamics and quantum mechanics (QM)] that unconventional (GVL)C–H...O(ethanol) HB interactions also play an important role. This finding indicates that GVL exhibits at least a weak HB donor ability, which could also manifest in its pure form.

In analogy to GVL, the complexation behavior of acetone (which is similar to that of ACN⁵⁴) is predominantly attributed to dipolar interactions by some researchers,^{54,57} while others ascribe it to HB interactions,^{58,63} or a combination of both,⁶⁴ as recently discussed by NguyenHuynh et al.⁴⁶ The latter option, referring to the simultaneous occurrence of both HB and dipolar interactions in DNS-based fluids, appears natural and reasonable because HB interactions, as a chemical concept, result from a combined effect of multiple physical forces including electrostatics (e.g., dipole–dipole interactions), charge-transfer, induction, and dispersions.^{61,65,66}

Therefore, it may not be completely clear whether or not the association term should be employed when modeling the properties of pure DNSs with PC-SAFT. This is mainly because their HB donor ability may not be necessarily negligible, as indicated in refs 51, 58, 63, and 64. However, it is worth noting that this term was originally designed to describe molecular

associations in a general sense, not exclusively HB interactions.³³ Therefore, describing the formation of DNS⋯DNS complexes using the association term would sound quite meaningful regardless of the question of whether the physical interaction is of the dipolar or HB origin. This idea was explored by von Solms et al.,⁶⁷ who treated polar molecules, including acetone, as self-associating using the simplified PC-SAFT EOS⁶⁸ without incorporating any dipolar term. This “pseudo-association” approach was later tested also by other authors^{46,69,70} and typically yielded improved results for both pure compounds and mixtures, compared to the completely nonself-association approach with respect to DNSs. Such results are encouraging, regardless of whether the pseudo-association concept has or lacks a physical justification. However, modeling DNSs as polar but nonself-associating remains the prevailing strategy within the PC-SAFT framework.^{11,12,32,42–45,47,48,60} This highlights the need for further investigation in this area.^{46,69}

For completeness, although the ability of DNSs to form HB between themselves is ambiguous, it is quite clear that they can participate in cross-HB interactions in mixtures with molecules possessing HB donor sites, such as alcohols and water.^{43,66,67} Therein, DNSs act as HB acceptors due to their lone electron pairs. In the case of GVL, these induced cross-associations (often termed solvation) were confirmed both spectroscopically^{49,50} and computationally.⁵¹ These important effects can also be taken into account using the association term of PC-SAFT.^{43,71} However, the cross-associations are not considered in this study, as it exclusively focuses on the properties of pure DNSs.

The interactional intricacies outlined above illustrate the challenges associated with proper modeling of DNSs and their properties. For thermodynamic models including SAFT EOSs, the selection of a modeling and parametrization strategy generally impacts the outcomes regarding both pure components and mixture properties. Our previous studies on the performance of various PC-SAFT-type models for DNSs, including GVL¹¹ and dihydrolevoglucosenone,¹⁴ interestingly indicated a somewhat ambiguous effect of the explicit inclusion of the high dipole moment (specified by experiment or QM calculation). While it appears to be essential for a reasonable description of some properties [e.g., liquid–liquid equilibria (LLE) in mixtures with hydrocarbons], it has a negative impact on the model accuracy for other properties (e.g., heat capacity of a pure DNS). Therefore, the goal of the current work is to explore and compare the performance of various modeling strategies within the PC-SAFT EOS for pure DNSs in more detail, including nonpolar, explicitly dipolar, and pseudo-associating approaches. To this end, a broader set of six different DNSs and four pure-compound properties are considered. Specifically, the six DNSs are GVL (CAS: 108-29-2), PC (CAS: 108-32-7), ACN (CAS: 75-05-8), dihydrolevoglucosenone (DLG; CAS: 53716-82-8), 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (NMP; CAS: 872-50-4), and sulfolane (SUL; CAS: 126-33-0). Regarding applications, ACN, NMP, and SUL are conventional “nongreen” DNSs, while GVL, PC, and DLG represent novel and sustainable alternatives.^{13,15,16,19,72} The pure-compound properties include the liquid density (ρ^{liq}), vapor pressure (p^{sat}), enthalpy of vaporization (Δh_{vap}), and residual isobaric liquid heat capacity (c_p^{res} ; i.e., the difference between the isobaric heat capacity of liquid and ideal gas). Based on a comprehensive computational evaluation of the results for the fluid-phase thermodynamic properties of pure DNSs, the merits and drawbacks of the considered strategies are discussed, also in

the context of the values of dipole moments and other pure-compound parameters.

The next section describes the computational details and the PC-SAFT modeling strategies considered. The results obtained are then presented and analyzed in Section 3. Finally, the observations are summarized and contextualized in the last section.

2. COMPUTATIONAL METHODS

2.1. PC-SAFT EOS and Its Configurations. PC-SAFT views molecules as chains composed of spherical segments that can interact with each other. It calculates the residual Helmholtz energy, a^{res} , by summing individual contributions reflecting the structural and interactional characteristics of the chains (molecules):^{30–32}

$$a^{\text{res}} = a^{\text{hc}} + a^{\text{disp}} + a^{\text{DD}} + a^{\text{assoc}} \quad (1)$$

In eq 1, the term a^{hc} includes repulsive interactions, closely related to the size of a molecular hard chain (hc), which are described by the number of spherical segments forming a chain (m) and their diameter (σ).

The dispersion interactions are described by the term a^{disp} and parametrized using compound-specific dispersion energy parameter (u/k_B ; k_B denotes the Boltzmann constant).

The dipolar term a^{DD} accounts for the dipole–dipole interactions of permanent dipoles (μ). Several dipolar theories have been proposed^{3,32,59–61,73–75} (see Section 3.6 for further information). In this work, we employed the dipolar term due to Gross and Vrabec³² (GV), which is widely used with PC-SAFT^{11,37,43,44,48,76–78} and was recently found to show a slightly better overall performance than the other terms for molecules with higher dipole moments.⁶¹ The GV dipolar contribution for nonspherical molecules was derived using a third-order perturbation theory and assumes that the dipole moment is oriented axially to the molecular axis. This seems to match with the asymmetric electron distribution in molecules of DNSs shown in Figure 1. In the GV term, the integrals related to the correlation functions are approximated by power series in density whose coefficients were fitted to comprehensive molecular simulation data.³² (We also examined, to a lesser extent, an additional dipolar term due to Jog and Chapman,⁵⁹ with the results presented in Section 3.6.)

Association interactions, such as HB, are explicitly accounted for through the term a^{assoc} , which is common to different SAFT versions. A detailed description of the contributions to a^{res} in eq 1 can be found in the original papers.^{30–32,79} From a^{res} , other thermodynamic properties can be calculated, including those considered in this work.^{30,80}

However, the terms a^{DD} and a^{assoc} on the right-hand side of eq 1 are not always used. For nonpolar substances (with $\mu \rightarrow 0$), such as hydrocarbons, eq 1 reduces to $a^{\text{res}} = a^{\text{hc}} + a^{\text{disp}}$. In this case, only three parameters per compound have to be known (m , σ , and u/k_B). For polar but nonself-associating substances including DNSs, it typically reads $a^{\text{res}} = a^{\text{hc}} + a^{\text{disp}} + a^{\text{DD}}$. This model configuration with the GV term as a^{DD} is sometimes referred to as PCP-SAFT³² (PC polar SAFT) or PCP-SAFT-GV and requires the dipole moment in addition to m , σ , and u/k_B . a^{assoc} requires two additional parameters for an associating component to be known: the association energy ($\epsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B$) and the effective association volume (κ^{assoc}). Furthermore, the so-called association scheme (N^{assoc}) must be specified, i.e., the number of different association sites. For self-associating substances, such as water and alcohols (and DNSs, if

Figure 2. Molecular models of GVL in form of the hard-sphere representation inherent to the PC-SAFT-type EOSs for (a) MS1, (b) MS2 and MS3, and (c) MS4. The arrow in (b) represents the dipole moment, which is restricted to stretch over two segments at most according to the model theory.³² The small solid circles in (c) represent the association sites.

Table 1. Reference Data and Their Temperature Ranges^a (in K) and Sources

DNS	$(\rho^{\text{liq}})^b$	p^{sat}	Δh_{vap}	$(c_p^{\text{res}})^c$
GVL	288–453 ^{11,96}	240–480 ⁹²	240–480 ⁹²	265–358 ⁹²
PC	298–368 ⁹⁷	260–440 ⁹²	260–440 ⁹²	220–420 ⁹²
ACN	255–455 ⁹⁸	280–490 ⁹⁹	298 ¹⁰⁰	230–300 ^{101,102}
DLG	293–353 ^{14,103}	253–403 ¹⁴	253–403 ¹⁴	260–350 ¹⁴
NMP	253–373 ^{104–107}	265–525 ⁹¹	260–520 ⁹¹	265–355 ⁹¹
SUL	303–373 ¹⁰⁶	300–530 ⁹⁰	300–530 ⁹⁰	305–355 ⁹⁰

^aThe temperature ranges are significantly below the critical points of the compounds,¹⁰⁸ except for ACN, whose maximum temperature of 490 K considered corresponds to $0.9 \cdot T_c$. ^bAt $p = 0.1$ MPa, except for ACN, for which saturated ρ^{liq} were considered. ^cAt $p = 0.1$ MPa. For all DNSs except ACN, the single source of c_p^{res} includes c_p for both the liquid and ideal gas phases. For ACN, c_p^{liq} was taken from ref 101, while that for the ideal gas was taken from ref 102.

relevant^{46,67}), eq 1 is usually used in the form $a^{\text{res}} = a^{\text{hc}} + a^{\text{disp}} + a^{\text{assoc}}$, i.e., without the dipolar term. The simultaneous description and separation of dipolar (a^{DD}) and association (a^{assoc}) interactions is possible but rather challenging and uncommon within SAFT EOSs.^{3,43,46,66,76,81} This scarcity arises because (i) a^{assoc} and its parameters are often assumed to implicitly capture the effects of dipole moments,^{82,83} and (ii) simultaneously applying both a^{DD} and a^{assoc} increases the number of required parameters that potentially describe qualitatively similar effects on physicochemical properties.^{3,66} This may introduce certain parametrization challenges, mainly associated with the well-known issue of parameter degeneracy,^{42,76,84} where PC-SAFT parameters for associating compounds can often be obtained in multiple degenerate sets, each yielding comparable modeling results. However, these challenges can be mitigated by prespecifying some parameters using independent sources^{3,32,46,78} or by employing advanced parametrization approaches^{85,86} (see below).

For most chemicals, including solvents like DNSs, the compound-specific parameters m , σ , u/k_B , and eventually $\epsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B$ and κ^{assoc} are usually determined by fitting them to experimental data on the properties of pure compounds. Data on ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} are most commonly used for this purpose,^{3,30,32,68,79,87} although richer data sets, which include properties such as the isobaric thermal expansivity, c_p^{res} , speed of sound, or surface tension (in addition to ρ^{liq} and p^{sat}) are also occasionally used.^{80,88,89} However, using these richer data sets increases parametrization costs and can somewhat impede the evaluation of predictive capabilities of a model, particularly in terms of the pure-compound properties. Finally, the dipole moment μ can be adjusted (e.g., fitted together with the other parameters), or specified before the parameter optimization procedure.³² In the latter case, experiment- or QM-based dipole moments can be used.

2.2. PC-SAFT Modeling Strategies and Parametrizations Applied. In total, four different PC-SAFT modeling strategies (MSs) were considered for each of the DNSs. These strategies differed in the treatment of the strongly dipolar nature of DNSs. Specifically, the four MSs were as follows:

MS1. A PC-SAFT model without a dipolar term that considers DNSs to be nonpolar and nonself-associating (with $\mu = 0$ D, $a^{\text{DD}} = 0$, and $a^{\text{assoc}} = 0$). This model contains three adjusted parameters (m , σ , and u/k_B).

MS2. A PCP-SAFT model with the GV dipolar term explicitly considering a DNS to be dipolar but nonself-associating ($a^{\text{assoc}} = 0$), with a specified value of μ (calculated independently by QM with a polarizable continuum model, as described below) and with three adjusted parameters (m , σ , and u/k_B).

MS3. A PCP-SAFT model with the GV dipolar term explicitly considering a DNS to be dipolar but nonself-associating ($a^{\text{assoc}} = 0$), with μ being an adjustable parameter regressed together with m , σ , and u/k_B (four adjusted parameters).

MS4. A PC-SAFT model without any dipolar term ($a^{\text{DD}} = 0$) but with the association term that considers a DNS to be self-associating with five adjustable parameters (m , σ , u/k_B , $\epsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B$, and κ^{HB}), thus reviving the “pseudo-association” concept proposed by von Solms et al.⁶⁷ The association scheme “2 (1, 1)” was used for all DNSs, which comprises a total of two association sites, one “positive” (e.g., HB donor) and one “negative” (HB acceptor) site (it is also known as 2B association scheme⁷⁹).

These MSs cover the three fundamental approaches to modeling dipolar compounds within SAFT:^{34,59} (i) a nonpolar approach where dipolar effects are accounted for only implicitly through fitted (large) u/k_B values (MS1), (ii) an explicitly dipolar approach (MS2 and MS3), and (iii) an approach where dipolar effects are mapped using the association contribution (MS4).

Illustrations of a GVL molecule within the PC-SAFT hard-sphere representation for each MS are provided in Figure 2 (compare with the electrostatic potential map of GVL in Figure 1). The number of segments reflects the values obtained for the parameter m within each MS, as detailed in Table 2. (Although the number of segments m is noninteger, it was rounded to the nearest integer for illustration purposes in Figure 2, to display only complete segments. For GVL, this rounding is not a significant approximation, given the actual m values for MS1, MS3, and MS4 in Table 2.)

Table 2. PC-SAFT Parameters^a for the DNSs Considered in This Work

MS	<i>m</i>	$\sigma/\text{\AA}$	$(u/k_B)/\text{K}$	μ/D	$(\epsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B)/\text{K}$	κ^{assoc}	N^{assoc}
				GVL			
MS1	3.0113	3.5713	353.04				
MS2	3.7811	3.3017	228.99	6.18 ^b			
MS3	3.0910	3.5413	326.21	3.8277			
MS4	4.1358	3.1392	210.31		1950.8	1.5926	2 (1, 1)
				PC			
MS1	2.9036	3.5047	393.09				
MS2	4.2307	3.0888	178.14	7.35 ^b			
MS3	2.8832	3.5150	388.27	2.5470			
MS4	3.9319	3.1124	242.24		1952.8	1.5484	2 (1, 1)
				ACN			
MS1	2.0730	3.2966	334.83				
MS2	2.9110	2.9590	114.37	4.85 ^b			
MS3	2.3101	3.1727	228.43	3.6763			
MS4	3.0340	2.7692	160.18		1697.5	1.7522	2 (1, 1)
				DLG			
MS1 ^c	3.4155	3.5050	343.20				
MS2 ^c	3.8872	3.3565	270.99	5.55 ^b			
MS3	3.4176	3.5039	342.86	1.1430			
MS4	3.3663	3.5302	343.79		70.089	0.6356	2 (1, 1)
				NMP			
MS1	3.1273	3.5292	344.13				
MS2	3.5522	3.3870	258.21	5.60 ^b	0		
MS3	3.1085	3.5421	331.92	3.3488	0		
MS4	3.1599	3.5324	328.23	0	200.45	1.5 ^d	2 (1, 1)
				SUL			
MS1	2.8507	3.6755	430.54				
MS2	3.7219	3.3650	260.17	7.08 ^b			
MS3	2.8729	3.6722	412.74	3.5646			
MS4	3.0517	3.5824	333.71		1693.1	0.7408	2 (1, 1)

^aAll fitted to the pure-compound ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} data. ^bSpecified before the parameter regression. ^cTaken from Jeřábek et al.¹⁴ ^dSpecified before the parameter regression because of extremely large and small values of κ^{assoc} and $\epsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_B$, respectively (see the text).

For each DNS, the sets of adjustable pure compound parameters for the four modeling strategies were identified by fitting them to the reference data on ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} , as usual for solvents within the SAFT framework, to maintain the predictive approach. (MS1 and MS2 for DLG have already been presented in our recent contribution.¹⁴) To ensure consistency and facilitate fair comparison, we used the same reference data and fitting routines for all four MSs for each DNS. The sources and temperature ranges of these reference data are provided in Table 1. In most cases, we did not use primary experimental data, but their correlations provided in the original papers, for example, using the Cox or Clarke–Glew equations for p^{sat} (this allows for more convenient and flexible handling of the reference data, as well as easier automation of calculations). Therefore, we call these reference data “pseudo-experimental”. For p^{sat} , Δh_{vap} , and c_p^{res} , we preferred the consistent and recommended data sets produced by prof. Růžička and co-workers^{14,90–92} using the method of simultaneous correlation⁹³ based on precise and critically assessed experimental data. The parameters were determined using the simulated annealing optimization method^{85,94} (as in our previous studies^{37,39,95}), which resembles a global optimization approach by exploring a large parameter space and minimizing the possibility of being trapped in a local minimum. Closer details on this method and its setup can be found in refs 37 and 85. The objective function, which was minimized in the parameter optimization procedure, was used in the common form:

$$F_{\text{obj}} = \frac{1}{N_p} \sum_{i=1}^{N_p} \left(\frac{\rho_{\text{calc}}^{\text{liq}} - \rho_{\text{exp}}^{\text{liq}}}{\rho_{\text{exp}}^{\text{liq}}} \right)_i^2 + \frac{1}{N_p} \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \left(\frac{p_{\text{calc}}^{\text{sat}} - p_{\text{exp}}^{\text{sat}}}{p_{\text{exp}}^{\text{sat}}} \right)_j^2 \quad (2)$$

In eq 2, N_p and N_p denote the number of pseudo-experimental data points for ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} , respectively. The subscripts “exp” and “calc” denote the pseudo-experimental data and those calculated with PC-SAFT, respectively. The parameter values obtained for MS1 to MS4 are provided in Table 2 and discussed in more detail in Section 3.1. For all calculations performed in this work with PC(P)-SAFT, including the parameter optimization, we utilized our in-house Fortran codes.

In the case of MS2, the dipole moment values were specified before the parameter regression and are shown in Table S1. They were calculated in the Gaussian 16 software (revision C.01)⁵² at the MP2/aug-cc-pVTZ level of theory with Polarizable Continuum Model (PCM)¹⁰⁹ to emulate the condensed-phase state of pure DNSs. These single-point calculations were performed at the optimal molecular geometries determined using MP2/6-311++g(d,p). The use of PCM was motivated by the fact that the dipole moments of polar substances are higher in the bulk liquid phase than in the gas phase^{44,110,111} (the difference typically reach 20–50%). The relative permittivities of the considered DNSs used in the PCM calculation are provided in Table S1. For comparison purposes, we also calculated gas-phase dipole moment values, at the same

QM level but without PCM, and compared them with their experimental counterparts (also shown in Table S1). In the context of the formulation of a^{DD} , we consider all DNSs to contain a single polar group (with the number of segments, n_{μ} , equal to unity;³² see Section 3.6), allowing the use of molecular dipole moments (as usual for DNSs^{32,44,45,47}), instead of multiple group-based μ with $n_{\mu} > 1$.

It should be noted that the DNSs considered here have previously been parametrized within PC-SAFT in various studies,^{11,44,47,48,112,113} covering both nonpolar and polar regimes. However, we opted not to utilize these parametrizations mainly because they were determined using different reference data and temperature ranges, which could introduce inconsistency and bias into our comparison. Furthermore, the reference data used for these older parametrizations may now be outdated due to ongoing advancements in knowledge of the physicochemical properties of pure DNSs.^{14,48,92}

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and discusses the performance of the four modeling strategies within PC-SAFT for the pure-compound properties of the considered DNSs. The obtained results in terms of relative deviations (RD; see Table S2 for its definition) from the pseudo-experimental data as a function of temperature are shown in Figures S1–S6. The average absolute relative deviation (AARD; Table S2) values between the pseudo-experimental data and the data calculated with the considered strategies are displayed in Figure 4.

3.1. Pure-Compound Parameter Values. First, the values of the pure-compound parameters obtained for the considered DNSs within the four modeling strategies are inspected and discussed. These values are shown in Table 2.

For MS1, the obtained parameter values correspond to the values typically obtained for strongly polar DNSs within the nonpolar PC-SAFT treatment.^{11,32,47} These are characterized by quite high u/k_{B} values above approximately 330 K that numerically compensate the missing explicit treatment of the high dipole moments of DNSs. For comparison, u/k_{B} values for (cyclo)alkanes and esters are typically around 250 K.³⁰ In the case of SUL, the u/k_{B} parameter value reached even 430 K, but values above 390 K for SUL within a nonpolar treatment are not surprising,^{112,113} as they have to compensate for a significant dipole moment of SUL (see the following paragraph).

Regarding the explicitly polar MS2 approach, the corresponding PCM-based dipole moment values (μ^{PCM}) can be seen in Table S1. This table also shows that they are 23–40% higher than those in vacuum (μ^{gas}), and that some of them are quite high, such as those of PC and SUL that are above 7 D.

The inclusion of MS3 in this work allows for a comparison of the optimal μ values (μ^{opt}) regressed to ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} data and μ values calculated theoretically using QM (both in PCM and vacuum). This comparison is shown in Figure 3 by means of a parity plot. For all DNSs, the optimized dipole moments have values lower than those obtained from QM. However, for all six DNSs, the gas-phase dipole moments agree much better with the optimized values than those based on PCM. For ACN as an example, the μ^{opt} value of 3.7 D harmonizes well with 3.9 D obtained from both QM/vacuum and experiment, as shown in Table S1. This indicates that the gas-phase μ values are a better alternative for DNSs to use within the PCP-SAFT framework, although the PCM-based μ should theoretically align more closely with the dipole moment values in the liquid phase. The best agreement between μ^{opt} and $\mu^{\text{QM,gas}}$ is found for ACN and

Figure 3. Comparison of the dipole moments of the considered DNSs optimized to ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} data within MS3 (μ^{opt}) with those calculated using QM (μ^{QM}) in PCM (solid symbols; used in MS2) and vacuum (empty symbols; used in MS2.5).

NMP, while the poorest agreement is exerted by PC and, particularly, DLG. For the latter, μ^{opt} reached a very low value slightly above 1 D.

Therefore, we determined an additional set of PCP-SAFT parameters for each DNS using the specified μ^{gas} values. This fifth set is provided for potential users in Table S3, along with the corresponding statistical deviations. Since its results fall between those of MS2 and MS3, the strategy is referred to as MS2.5, and its results are not further discussed in this paper.

Currently, two possible explanations can be provided for the relatively low μ^{opt} values obtained and the superiority of μ^{gas} over μ^{PCM} . The first explanation (physical) consists in that the antiparallel configuration of the DNS molecules in dimers in the liquid, in which the molecular dipoles are oppositely aligned, leads to a partial cancelation of the effects of the dipole moments,⁴⁷ thus lowering the average effective dipole moment, as observed for μ^{opt} . The second possible rationalization (technical) is that the large dipole moments of DNSs may approach or even exceed the upper bound of validity of the current dipolar theories with respect to μ . To inspect this, the obtained μ^{gas} , μ^{PCM} , and μ^{opt} values were recalculated as reduced dipole moments,³² μ^* ($\mu^* = \mu/\sqrt{m\sigma^3u}$), which are shown in Table S1. The available dipolar theories were developed and tested within certain ranges of μ^* values.^{32,59,61,114} For example, the GV term³² was developed assuming fluids with $\mu^* \leq 2.5$; other theories considered even lower values.^{3,59} As shown in Table S1, the gas-phase μ^* values for some DNSs exceed these boundaries, while those calculated by PCM are consistently higher (even above 4 in some cases). Furthermore, dipolar perturbation theories are known to have poor convergence behavior, especially for high μ .^{3,61,73,111} Although the Padé approximant, which is commonly used to express polar perturbation expansions, should perform well up to very high dipole moments,¹¹¹ it cannot be excluded that the relatively large μ values of DNS molecules might negatively impact the behavior of a^{DD} (e.g., by falling outside the series expansion's radius of convergence, particularly for nonspherical chain-like molecules like DNSs). The above aspects may also explain why, when μ was treated as adjustable within MS3, the values relaxed to quite low μ^* values (see Table S1), remaining below a boundary of roughly 4 D (or $\mu^* \approx 2.5$), as illustrated in Figure 3. This value may correlate with the maximum μ^* considered in the development of the GV term.

Figure 4. AARD values obtained from PC-SAFT with the different modeling strategies for the considered pure-compound properties: (a) liquid density, (b) vapor pressure, (c) enthalpy of vaporization, and (d) residual isobaric liquid heat capacity. Figure (e) displays the total AARD calculated over all four properties.

In the case of MS2 and MS3, the values of u/k_B are accordingly lower as a result of the application of a^{DD} that explicitly covers the effects of dipolar interactions. The decrease of u/k_B when switching from MS1 to MS2 or MS3 is roughly proportional to the dipole moment values used in these “dipolar” strategies, as illustrated in Figure S7a. This also explains that the u/k_B values of MS2 are always lower than their MS3 counterparts because the PCM-based dipole moments in MS2 are generally greater than those obtained within MS3. The only outlying points in Figure S7a are those of ACN, which foreshadows somewhat tricky results for this DNS (see the following sections).

Regarding the pseudo-association MS4, the values of the association energy parameter ϵ^{assoc}/k_B for GVL, PC, ACN, and SUL obtained within MS4 reached 1700 to 1950 K. These values appear reasonable because they are (i) between those typically found for, e.g., 1-alkanols (2500–3000 K^{31,95}) and moderately polar compounds such as ethers (≈ 1000 K)^{67,69} and (ii) in agreement with those found for ketones when treated as self-associating (1300–1900 K).^{67,69} Furthermore, they are close to binding energies of acetone and GVL dimers reported in the literature (1620 and 2300 K, respectively).^{8,63} These are some of the aspects that would justify the consideration of DNSs as self-associating within SAFT.

However, the ϵ^{assoc}/k_B values obtained for DLG and NMP are extremely small and even lower than the corresponding values of u/k_B . This occasionally happens for DNSs^{67,113} as well as moderately polar substances, pharmaceuticals,³⁷ or other chemicals,¹¹⁵ and suggests that MS4 is not an efficient choice in these cases, as it brings no improvement in the model performance compared to MS1 at the cost of two additional parameters to fit. (For clarity, we note that these low ϵ^{assoc}/k_B values do not negatively affect the accuracy of MS4, as it yields results that are as excellent as those of MS1 for both DLG and NMP, as illustrated in the following sections.) An extreme situation in this regard was observed for NMP, for which the simulated annealing procedure tended to determine a too low ϵ^{assoc}/k_B value (below 50 K) and a very high κ^{assoc} value (above 7). To address this issue and obtain more reasonable values of

ϵ^{assoc}/k_B and κ^{assoc} for NMP, two approaches were examined: (i) reducing the number of regressed parameters from five to four by fixing the κ^{assoc} value at 1.5, which is consistent with those obtained for GVL, PC, and ACN within MS4, and (ii) including the c_p^{res} data for NMP, in addition to ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} , in the objective function (eq 2) for the regression of all five parameters, including κ^{assoc} . Surprisingly, both approaches yielded very similar results. First, the c_p^{res} -based approach determined κ^{assoc} to be 1.59, which is very close to the fixed $\kappa^{assoc} = 1.5$ used in approach (i). The values of the other parameters were also quite similar: for example, u/k_B values were 328 and 324 K, and ϵ^{assoc}/k_B values were 200 and 266 K for approaches (i) and (ii), respectively. Although these ϵ^{assoc}/k_B values remain quite low, they are more reasonable and comparable to those of the respective dispersion parameters. This outcome demonstrates the potential of including c_p^{res} data in parameter determination to guide the regression toward more reasonable values (interestingly, it also reduced the computational time of the regression procedure by 25% compared to 5-parameter MS4, indicating a better convergence behavior). While approach (ii) provided, of course, lower $AARD(c_p^{res})$, that from approach (i) was not significantly worse (0.9% and 2.8%, respectively). Therefore, to maintain the predictive nature of the calculations with respect to c_p^{res} , only the MS4 parameter set with the fixed κ^{assoc} was considered further in this work, as shown in Table 2. Fixing κ^{assoc} is a common practice and sometimes even necessary to achieve reasonable parameter values for complex substances.^{36,37,116}

In the case of DLG, the low ϵ^{assoc}/k_B value correlates with the low value of μ^{opt} obtained for this DNS within MS3, both diminishing the importance of a^{DD} or a^{assoc} in the MS3 and MS4 calculations, respectively. This also causes MS3 and MS4 to almost reduce to the nonpolar MS1, which is further evidenced by (i) the similar m , σ , and u/k_B values obtained for DLG within MS1, MS3, and MS4 (see Table 2) and (ii) the fact that the results of these three strategies form a “bundle” of close curves (see Figure S4). As a result, the explicit inclusion of dipolar or association interactions does not appear critical to capture the behavior of pure DLG. However, we recently showed that a^{DD} is

crucial to achieve a reasonable description of LLE in mixtures of DLG with hydrocarbons.¹⁴

Furthermore, Figure S7b suggest that the mutual correlation between $\epsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_{\text{B}}$ from MS4 and μ^{opt} from MS3 is not completely general. However, if the point for NMP (denoted with an exclamation mark) is excluded from the evaluation (because it was obtained with a fixed κ^{assoc}), the coefficient of determination, R^2 , of the remaining points reaches 0.73, indicating a relatively strong correlation.

3.2. Liquid Density. In the case of ρ^{liq} (and p^{sat}), it is *correlative* performance that is evaluated, as these data were used directly in the parameter fitting procedure through eq 2. Therefore, the model errors typically achieve low values for these two properties. As can be seen in Figure 4a, all modeling strategies excellently reproduce ρ^{liq} with AARD(ρ^{liq}) values below 0.6% for all considered DNSs except ACN. Taking into account the results for all six DNSs, the best results for ρ^{liq} were obtained with MS4, followed by MS3 and MS1, while the largest error was achieved by MS2. However, even the total AARD(ρ^{liq}) produced by MS2 does not exceed 1.6%, including the problematic results for ACN.

None of the considered models except MS2 appears to show any tendency toward a poor description of density at either low or high temperatures. However, the temperature ranges of ρ^{liq} for some DNSs (Table 1) may be too narrow to provide a complete picture. In some cases (e.g., GVL and PC), the models exhibit a less accurate representation of the temperature dependence of ρ^{liq} , which is related to the isobaric thermal expansivity. As a result, the absolute errors are highest at the edges of the considered T intervals and may potentially be even greater beyond these ranges.

For ACN, all modeling strategies except MS4 exert significantly higher AARD(ρ^{liq}) values than for the other DNSs. This can (at least partially) be attributed to the fact that the reference data on (saturated) ρ^{liq} of ACN covered a wide temperature interval up to $0.83 \cdot T_{\text{c}}$ (see Table 1; T_{c} is the critical temperature), while the T intervals for the other DNSs were narrower and only up to $\approx 0.6 \cdot T_{\text{c}}$ at most. Furthermore, Kleiner and Gross⁴⁷ also reported both nonpolar and polar PC-SAFT models to provide considerably higher AARD(ρ^{liq}) values (above 6%) for ACN than for the other DNSs. In particular, the AARD value for ρ^{liq} of ACN above 8% achieved by MS2 can be an extremely large error in the context of applications. Moreover, as shown in Figure S3, individual data points at temperatures above 400 K have even larger errors up to 30%. (This drastic increase in error with increasing T is also associated with the fact that MS2 predicts a substantially lower T_{c} value for ACN than the other strategies.) In contrast, the results for ρ^{liq} of ACN obtained from MS4 are excellent.

The overall accuracy of the MSs for ρ^{liq} is in the following order: MS2 < MS1 < MS3 < MS4. However, as Figure 4a reveals, the differences among them are numerically quite small (except for those of ACN). This order appears to correlate with the number of adjustable parameters (i.e., 3, 3, 4, and 5, respectively) and, thus, with the flexibility of the respective MS. It is surprising that MS1, the PC-SAFT model that neglects any explicit treatment of the large dipole moments of DNSs, outperforms MS2 with its fixed (and large) μ from QM.

Finally, the obtained AARD(ρ) values are contextualized with the uncertainties of the reference pseudo-experimental data. The overall uncertainty can be estimated by combining two terms: the experimental uncertainty and that associated with correlations of the primary data. For the former, most density

data were determined using vibrating-tube densimetry,^{11,14,97,106} with reported relative uncertainties on the order of 10^{-4} (except for ACN, where the relative uncertainty⁹⁸ equals $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$). The uncertainties from the fit are either lower or of the same order of magnitude as the experimental ones. Consequently, for the conditions considered in this work, only the PC-SAFT results with AARD(ρ^{liq}) values below 0.1% are within, or at least closely approaching, the overall relative uncertainty of the pseudo-experimental density data. This applies to the very best results obtained from MS1, MS3, and MS4, as detailed in Table S2.

3.3. Vapor Pressure. Next, we focus on the ability of the MSs to reproduce the vapor pressure data. For p^{sat} , the strategies qualitatively follow the same “behavioral” pattern as for the liquid density. Specifically, the accuracy again increases in the order MS2 < MS1 < MS3 < MS4. The highest AARDs are again observed for ACN. All strategies except MS2 give AARD(p^{sat}) values below 1%, even for ACN. This can be considered as excellent, as such small errors are not always obtained even for less polar substances.^{30,32} Moreover, it appears that even individual data points within the considered temperature ranges do not exceed RD values of 1% or 2%—once again, except for MS2—as shown in Figures S1–S6.

MS2 provided the least accurate representations of p^{sat} . The corresponding AARDs reach 2% to 9%, with the latter observed, not surprisingly, for ACN. Figure S3 shows that this high deviation value is mainly caused by data points at temperatures below 350 K, where the corresponding RDs reach even -20% . This is also associated with incorrectly capturing the temperature dependence of p^{sat} , indicating that the MS3 model, with the high PCM-based dipole moments, is not as flexible as the other strategies.

Overall relative uncertainties of the pseudo-experimental p^{sat} data used are within the lower single-digit percentage range.^{14,90–92} As shown in Table S2, the AARD(p^{sat}) values for all MSs and DNSs (except for the MS2 result for ACN) are lower than or, at worst, comparable to these pseudo-experimental uncertainties.

3.4. Enthalpy of Vaporization. The enthalpy of vaporization is considered as an additional indicator of the quality of the EOS performance for the considered DNSs. Although Δh_{vap} was not directly used in the parameter regression, it is generally interrelated with p^{sat} through the Clapeyron equation (Δh_{vap} relates to the T -dependence of p^{sat}). Therefore, if an EOS represents p^{sat} and its temperature course well, it should theoretically provide a reasonable Δh_{vap} as well.

The AARD(Δh_{vap}) values obtained from the four MSs are shown in Figure 4c. For all DNSs except ACN, the strategies MS1, MS3, and MS4 provided excellent results with AARDs below 0.6% (these low errors also hold for individual data points at the whole T -range; see Figures S1 to S6). Given the typical relative uncertainty of the Δh_{vap} data,^{14,92,100} which is (often significantly) below 1%, the majority of Δh_{vap} results from MS1, MS3, and MS4, with AARDs below 0.6%, fall within or closely approach the pseudo-experimental uncertainty. Interestingly, the nonpolar MS1 slightly outperformed the polar MS3 (as well as MS2.5) for all DNSs except ACN, which somewhat contradicts other literature observations,³² although those observations were mainly made for less polar substances.

MS2 achieved an overall error of 2%. An inspection of Figures S1 to S6 reveals that the data points at the edges of the temperature intervals contribute the most to the resulting AARD values of MS2, while the smallest RD(Δh_{vap}) values are found in

the temperature interval of approximately 300–350 K. This is a consequence of the “diagonal” shape of $RD(\Delta h_{\text{vap}})$, showing the largest negative errors at lower temperatures and the largest positive errors at higher temperatures. This behavior corresponds to the U-shaped temperature dependence of $AARD(p^{\text{sat}})$. MS2 was surpassed not only by MS3 (with optimized μ) but also by the completely nonpolar MS1. This further indicates that the μ values obtained from the PCM calculation are too high to be used in the context of PC-SAFT. This is most visible in the case of ACN, for which MS2 gives very poor correlations of both ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} . As a result, when applying a dipolar PC-SAFT model to DNSs with dipole moments obtained from an independent external source, the ideal-gas values of μ appear to be a significantly better choice than those from PCM, as discussed in Section 3.1.

MS4 is the only model that describes ρ^{liq} , p^{sat} , and Δh_{vap} of ACN with a good accuracy comparable to those obtained for the other DNSs. A technical explanation is that a model with at least five adjustable parameters (MS4) is needed to reasonably model both ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} of ACN simultaneously. The physical explanation is that only the pseudo-association concept can correctly capture the interactional behavior of pure ACN, as also indicated by other studies.^{46,67} Finally, all models generally show a slight tendency to overestimate the vaporization enthalpy, especially at higher temperatures.

3.5. Residual Isobaric Liquid Heat Capacity. The (residual) heat capacity is an important thermodynamic parameter of fluids in the context of heat-transfer processes. At the same time, it is a second-order derivative of the Helmholtz energy which measures the reaction of the fluid to changes in temperature.

The overall $AARD(c_p^{\text{res}})$ values for the considered DNSs are displayed in Figure 4d. At first sight, it is obvious that $AARD(c_p^{\text{res}})$ values obtained from the four PC-SAFT models are generally much higher than those achieved for the other properties. However, this situation is normal, since c_p^{res} is very sensitive to model formulation and parametrization. Therefore, EOS, including cubic and SAFT-type ones, are known to have difficulties to correctly capture c_p^{res} , as demonstrated in previous studies.^{61,77,80,95}

The relative performance of the modeling strategies for c_p^{res} is $MS2 < MS3 < MS4 < MS1$. This means that the nonpolar MS1 outperformed MS4 this time (specifically, for 5 of the 6 DNSs), although the numerical differences between them are small, in most cases. The total $AARD(c_p^{\text{res}})$ values calculated over all six DNSs were about 5% for both MS1 and MS4, which can be considered as excellent, in the context of somewhat higher error values typically observed for this derivative property. The most impressive MS1 and MS4 estimations of c_p^{res} are seen for GVL, PC, and SUL (Figures S1, S2, and S6, respectively). Furthermore, both MS1 and MS4 correctly describe the temperature dependence of c_p^{res} , as the respective curves in Figures S1–S6 are almost parallel to the horizontal axis in most cases. This is not always the case when modeling this quantity with EOSs. The superiority of MS1 and MS4 for c_p^{res} can further be demonstrated by qualitative results. Figure 5 shows that they provide a more correct order of the considered DNSs with respect to their c_p^{res} values than the other strategies.

Figure 5 also illustrates that the applied strategies tend to underestimate c_p^{res} data. This is most visible in the case of MS2, whose individual errors can reach very large values, for example, around -100% for PC and ACN (see Figures S2 and S3, respectively).

Figure 5. Values of c_p^{res} calculated by the MSs (at 300 K and 0.1 MPa) in comparison with their experimental counterparts. The lines serve as guides to the eye.

Compared to MS2, the strategy with optimized μ values (MS3) dramatically improves the performance of PC-SAFT for c_p^{res} . However, MS3 generally does not provide better c_p^{res} (and Δh_{vap}) estimations than MS1. This can be surprising, given that MS3 includes a^{DD} and has extra flexibility due to the fourth adjustable parameter (μ). However, this is generally not abnormal, as an optimal fit for one set of properties does not automatically guarantee good performance for others.^{77,86} In this context, we remind the reader that MS3 generally outperforms MS1 for the fitted properties (ρ^{liq} and p^{sat}), as demonstrated in Sections 3.2 and 3.3, respectively.

For completeness, the relatively poorer performance of the considered models for c_p^{res} may be due to overfitting to ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} data. An improved description of c_p^{res} can be achieved, for example, by including c_p^{res} itself or another second-order derivative property in the parameter regression,^{80,117,118} as discussed in Sections 2.1 and 3.1.

3.6. Gross–Vrabec versus Jog–Chapman Dipolar Term. As mentioned in Section 2.1, there are more dipolar theories available for a^{DD} that treat the dipole–dipole interactions explicitly. Historically, the development of such theories started with so-called molecule-based approaches (e.g., Gubbins and Twu⁷³ and Saager and Fischer⁷⁴), where the polar molecule is considered to consist of a single (rather large) spherical segment with a centered dipole moment stretching over it. In such way, the dipolar interactions are only effectively mapped onto a chain-like molecule and are typically underestimated.^{34,59} Therefore, dipolar theories aiming at the segment level have been developed, to account for the nonspherical shape of molecules. The dipolar terms due Jog and Chapman,^{59,119} Gross and Vrabec,³² and Karakatsani and Economou⁶⁰ are widely used representatives of this segment-based approach. Further details about these terms can be found in the original papers or in comparative studies such as refs 61, 76, 77, and 114. We should also mention the theory developed by Langenbach³ (COFFEE), which, unlike the other perturbation theories, allows for the inclusion of molecules with noncentral dipoles and accounts for the ordering effects due to polar interactions through the mutual equilibrium orientation structure of a fluid. These features could be significant in the context of DNSs and their aggregation behavior discussed in Section 1. This section presents a comparison of a selected GV-based MS and an additional strategy that incorporates the Jog–Chapman (JC) term as a^{DD} , which is also widely referenced in the literature.^{42,76,77,114,120,121} Therefore, we limit our discussion

Figure 6. AARD values obtained from PC-SAFT with the Gross–Vrabec³² (MS3) and Jog–Chapman⁵⁹ (MS3-JC) dipolar terms for the considered pure-compound properties: (a) liquid density, (b) vapor pressure, (c) enthalpy of vaporization, and (d) residual isobaric liquid heat capacity. Figure (e) displays the total AARD calculated over all four properties.

to outlining the key similarities and differences between these two terms.

Both JC and GV terms were developed for chain-like molecules and follow, to some extent, older dipolar theories.^{73,74} While the JC term is based on Wertheim’s thermodynamic perturbation theory of first order^{122,123} and assumes a hard-sphere fluid as reference, the GV term was derived using a third-order perturbation theory with a Lennard-Jones fluid as reference. In the GV term, the correlation integrals were replaced by a power series in reduced density, and its constants were fitted to molecular simulation results of VLE for a model polar fluid, following the strategy of Saager and Fischer⁷⁴). In contrast to GV, the JC term considers the dipole moment to be oriented perpendicularly to the molecular axis. Although we previously found the GV term with its axial orientation of μ to generally align with the charge distribution in DNSs discussed in Section 2.1, we acknowledge that the perpendicular orientation may provide a better model for certain DNSs. Besides the dipole moment itself, the additional parameter related to a^{DD} is n_μ for GV and x_p for JC. The latter parameter represents the fraction of dipolar segments in the chain.⁵⁹ For compounds with only one dipolar function per chain, x_p should theoretically be equal to reciprocal number of segments, $x_p = 1/m$. However, it is more often the case that x_p is regressed,^{42,76,114,120} being the fourth adjustable parameter.

Because of the typical usage of PC-SAFT-JC as a 4-parameter EOS (m , σ , u/k_B , x_p), we choose MS3 for the mutual comparison. Specifically, the parameters and results of MS3 from Tables 2 and S1 were taken as is, while we developed an additional set for each DNS considering the JC term instead of GV. We used μ^{gas} for μ , while x_p was optimized. This additional strategy is referred to as MS3-JC. The obtained MS3-JC parameters, together with the corresponding deviations, are provided in Table S4. A graphical comparison of MS3 and MS3-JC in terms of the obtained AARDs is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 shows that the both 4-parameter models produce deviations in similar ranges, i.e., ρ^{liq} below 0.5%, p^{sat} below 1%, etc. (except for ACN). However, MS3-JC in most cases provides lower AARD values than MS3 for ρ^{liq} and p^{sat} , which indicates a better fitting properties. Furthermore, MS3-JC outperforms MS3 also for c_p^{res} for four of the six DNSs. The opposite is true for Δh_{vap} , where the GV-based MS3 dominates. These facts are best illustrated in the case of ACN, This which is quite surprising, as the linear nature of the ACN molecule, along with its electron distribution shown in Figure 1c, would suggest that the GV term with its axial orientation of μ is a more appropriate model than JC in this case.

Comparing the parameter values obtained within MS3 and MS3-JC (Tables 2 and S1, respectively), it can be seen that MS3-

JC tends to yield lower m and higher σ values compared to their MS3 counterparts. As a result, molecular representations within MS3-JC would have less number of larger segments per chain compared to Figure 2b. Regarding the dispersion energy parameter, u/k_B values of MS3-JC are, in most cases, considerably lower than those obtained within MS3. This correlates with the observations that the a^{DD} term due to JC is often of a larger quantitative significance for a^{res} than that of GV,⁷⁶ which can be explained by the more significant effect of the perpendicular orientation of μ on the system properties.³²

The deviation of the optimized x_p values from their theoretical counterparts ($x_p^{\text{theo}} = 1/m$) is shown by the column $x_p m$ in Table S4 (the more $x_p m$ is different from unity, the greater the deviation).⁴² For GVL and SUL, $x_p m \approx 1$, which means that MS3-JC could be used with x_p^{theo} and gas-phase dipole moment as is. However, the $x_p m$ values for the other DNSs are significantly different from unity. Specifically, $x_p m < 1$ are observed in most cases. This qualitatively indicates lowering of the effect of dipolar interactions and correlates with the relatively lower values of μ^{opt} observed for MS3, as discussed in Section 3.1.

To conclude this section, both MS3 and MS3-JC yielded qualitatively similar deviations, with the latter providing slightly more accurate results. In terms of the total AARD shown in Figure 6e, MS3-JC “won” for four of the six DNSs. This generally aligns with literature observations which report both PCP-SAFT-GV and PCP-SAFT-JC to perform comparably (with a slight superiority of one or the other in individual cases),^{32,76,77,114,121} despite the differences in both dipolar theories.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this work, four different modeling strategies within PC-SAFT for six DNSs were analyzed. They allowed evaluating and comparing the modeling results obtained (i) without the explicit inclusion of any dipolar interactions, (ii) with the explicit inclusion of them via the dipolar term of Gross and Vrabec,¹²⁴ and (iii) by mapping them using the association term. The pure-compound parameter sets were regressed in this work *de novo* (Tables 2, S3, and S4) using updated and critically evaluated experiment-based data; therefore, they can be recommended for further use within the PC-SAFT framework.

The nonpolar MS1 provided, in most cases, results comparable to those of MS3 and MS4, although it did not consider the strong dipolar effects explicitly. MS1 also clearly outperformed MS2 with its specified QM/PCM-based dipole moments. Although this has already been observed in the case of DLG,¹⁴ the general validity of this behavior also for the other DNSs can be surprising because explicitly capturing the large

condensed-phase dipole moments of DNSs in a modeling framework for pure DNSs would otherwise appear reasonable. This is even more remarkable when taking into account that MS1 has (like MS2) the smallest number of adjustable parameters (three) among the considered strategies.

The polar MS2 produced the worst results, indicating that the PCM-based μ values are too high for use within the PC-SAFT and, in general, that the μ value should be treated carefully in the context of DNSs. The latter generally aligns with literature observations of a drop in the accuracy of dipolar terms for higher values of μ .^{3,32,61} The question of which μ values are more appropriate has two principal answers. It appears that μ values optimized (MS3) together with the other parameters are generally the best choice (at the cost of introducing an additional regressed parameter). However, if a specified μ value from an external source is sought, *gas-phase* dipole moments, either from experiment or QM, appear to be a reasonable choice. However, both μ^{gas} and μ^{PCM} of DNSs can be, in many cases, substantially higher than those considered in the development of the current dipolar theories, as discussed in Section 3.1.

In the case of MS3, it can be argued that, rather than the explicit dipolar treatment itself, it is the presence of the fourth adjustable parameter that flexibilizes the model, leads to a better accuracy and makes the essential difference between MS3 and MS2 and MS1. However, MS3 sometimes produced slightly worse results than MS1, especially for the properties not explicitly considered in the parameter regression (Δh_{vap} and c_p^{res}). Therefore, the number of regressed parameters is not necessarily always the key factor.

The pseudo-association MS4 (five adjustable parameters) proved to be the winning strategy, as it provided the best overall results. The question of whether DNSs can technically be treated as self-associating within PC-SAFT is therefore positive, regardless of whether this representation is physically correct or not. This supports the considerations on the “absorption”/mapping of dipolar interactions in a^{assoc} . It also aligns with the original purpose of a^{assoc} itself, which was to describe associative interactions in general. Furthermore, the pseudo-association interactions in DNSs are not necessarily “pseudo”, as documented by the large body of literature on the significant association behavior of DNSs (after all, the term “associations” is commonly used in the context of interactional behavior of pure DNSs, whether it refers to the dipolar or HB origin of these interactions). For DLG and NMP, MS4 does not provide significant benefits over MS1 or MS3, as a result of the small values of the association parameters. This observation aligns with general considerations⁶⁷ that the association of DNSs is not a binary question (existing/nonexisting) but rather a question of intensity or degree, in the context of which different DNSs can behave differently. Finally, MS4 involves the greatest number of fitted parameters, which makes the minimal experimental data set¹²⁵ required in the fitting procedure larger than for the other strategies. However, the number of parameters can be reduced by specifying $\epsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_{\text{B}}$ using QM- or experiment-based binding energies of the DNS...DNS associates, since the $\epsilon^{\text{assoc}}/k_{\text{B}}$ values obtained within MS4 were in most cases comparable to those expected theoretically.

We also included one additional model with the Jog–Chapman dipolar term⁵⁹ instead of that due to Gross and Vrabec. The results indicate qualitatively comparable performance, with slightly better AARD values yielded from the JC term.

Further improvement in the performance for DNSs can be achieved by, for example, simultaneously applying both dipolar

and association terms,^{3,46} possibly using advanced dipolar theories such as COFFEE,³ together with sophisticated parameter optimization approaches.^{85,86}

Despite all the individual details discussed, it should not be overlooked that PC-SAFT, particularly with MS3 and MS4, enables a very relevant representation of the properties of DNSs in their pure fluid. However, to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the performance of various PC-SAFT modeling strategies for DNSs, it is imperative to consider not only their pure-substance properties but also their behavior in mixtures with other compounds. Exploring such mixtures will be the focus of our upcoming research.

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

SI Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acs.jced.4c00344>.

Dipole moment values calculated for the considered DNSs; AARD values of the properties of the pure DNSs calculated with the four PC-SAFT modeling strategies from their pseudo-experimental counterparts; temperature course of the respective relative deviations; PC-SAFT parameters for the DNSs considering additional modeling strategies with gas-phase dipole moments and the Jog–Chapman dipolar term; correlation between the dispersion and association energy parameters and dipole moments (PDF)

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Notes

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